

LANGUAGE INTERFERENCE IN ENGLISH: ITS TYPES AND EFFECTS

Yuldasheva Madina Shuxrat qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19137537>

Abstract:

This article examines the main types of language interference and its effect on the modern English. It focuses on phonetic, grammatical, lexical levels of interference and how they contribute to linguistic change in a bilingual context.

Keywords:

Language interference, language contact, phonetic interference, grammatical interference, lexical interference, lexical expansion

Introduction

In the contemporary world, English functions as a global language that serves as a tool of communication for speakers of different linguistic backgrounds. This language contact in multilingual societies creates a linguistic phenomenon known as language interference: the influence of one language on the structure of another language. Generally, interference is viewed negatively as source of errors in the second language acquisition. However, the modern linguistics considers this phenomenon not only a negative factor in language learning but also a driving force for the development of English. English continues to adapt to its global users, and interference is one of the key factors driving this process [Crystal, 2003]. The aim of this article is to explore how language interference on these various linguistic levels helps to reshape the English language, ultimately driving the expansion of its vocabulary and the diversification of its global forms.

The concept of interference was first introduced by U. Weinreich [1953], who defined it as deviations from the language norms caused by language contact. According to him, interference is most evident in those areas of language that have most clearly defined structure, namely in the system of basic phonemes, in morphology and syntax, and in certain aspects of vocabulary [Weinreich, 1953]. His work became foundation for further researches in this field. Later, T. Odlin [1989] describes interference as "cross-linguistic influence," where the features of one language system merge with another to create new linguistic variations. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova [2000], linguistic interference is a primary source of language enrichment, as the meeting of two cultures through language contact forces the vocabulary to expand and adapt. Furthermore, J. Jenkins [2000] views "interferences" as a positive evolution toward English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) that is a shared linguistic means of interaction. In this view, changes in pronunciation and grammar are a way for English to become a more efficient tool for international communication.

Types of Language Interference

Phonetic Interference

Phonetic interference arises when the sound system of speakers L1 influences their pronunciation in L2. A clear example is seen among many Uzbek learners of English, who regularly replace the sounds /θ/ and /ð/ with /s/ or /z/, pronouncing the word "think" as "sink". While a traditional pedagogy might call this an error, modern linguists consider it as a natural evolution. According to D. Hasanova, English in Uzbekistan is moving beyond being a "foreign" language and is instead becoming a localized variety with its own unique phonetic

identity like *Indian English* or *Australian English* [Hasanova, 2007]. Therefore, this type of interference fosters the creation of diverse pronunciation patterns and new accents, which help the language adapt to speakers from different linguistic backgrounds.

Grammatical Interference

Grammatical interference occurs when speakers apply the grammar rules of their native language to a foreign language. This often leads to incorrect and deviating use of sentence constructions and word order. A clear example of this is the use of the verb *to be* in English [Yartseva, 2018: 66]. In Russian, such a linking verb is absent, which often results in its incorrect lexical and grammatical use and/or its complete omission, in the speech of Russian-speaking individuals who are learning English. **For instance, a learner may say "She teacher" instead of "She is a teacher", directly transferring the structure of their native language into English.** From the perspective of B. Kachru, these deviations represent the "nativization" of the language, where the rigid rules of the Inner Circle (countries where English is the primary native language, such as the UK and USA) are modified to fit the communicative norms of the Expanding Circle (countries like Uzbekistan where English is used as a prominent foreign language). **This can** lead to new idiomatic expressions or sentence forms, contributing to the expansion of English in multicultural settings [Kachru,1992].

Lexical Interference

At the lexical level, interference is often driven by the similarity of lexical units between two languages; still, this is just one of the factors. As explained by S.G. Ter-Minasova [2000], language and culture are inseparable; it reflects a specific national worldview that may not have direct equivalents in another language, which creates *lexical gaps*. This frequently occurs when a target language lacks sufficient vocabulary to express these cultural concepts, speakers fill these gaps by adapting words from their native language. For instance, a speaker uses a native term for a specific local food or tradition that has no English equivalent. Additionally, as analyzed by V.V. Akulenko [1969], learners may be confused by the "*translator's false friends*" – lexical units that have similar form, but different meanings. A common example for Russian speakers is using the English word *actual* to mean "current" or *magazine* to mean "shop". Throughout history, English has borrowed many words from different languages, such as Latin and French. Words like *restaurant*, *ballet*, *auditorium* and *curriculum* are bright examples of borrowing. The lexical interference enriches English vocabulary and contributes to cultural exchange between language and society.

In conclusion, although interference is often associated with errors, it also plays a pivotal role in the development of English. The current article shows that phonetic, grammatical, and lexical changes are not just errors; they are the tools that allow English to adapt to new cultures. By creating new accents, unique sentence structures, and a richer vocabulary, interference ensures that English remains a flexible and global language. Moreover, language interference might contribute to linguistic diversity, flexibility, and the global spread of English.

References:

1. Akulenko V.V. Anglo-russkiy slovar' "lozhnykh druzey perevodchika" [English-Russian Dictionary of "Translator's False Friends"]. – Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1969. – 384 p.
2. Crystal D. English as a Global Language. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003. – 212 p.

3. Hasanova D. Broadening the boundaries of the Expanding Circle: English in Uzbekistan // World Englishes. – 2007. – Vol. 26, No. 3. – P. 276–290.
4. Jenkins J. The Phonology of English as an International Language. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000. – 251 p.
5. Kachru B. The Other Tongue: English across Cultures. – Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1992. – 384 p.
6. Odlin T. Language Transfer: Cross-linguistic influence in language learning. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989. – 210 p.
7. Ter-Minasova S.G. Language and Intercultural Communication. – Moscow: Slovo, 2000. – 164 p.
8. Weinreich U. Languages in Contact: Findings and Problems. – New York: Linguistic Circle of New York, 1953. – 148 p.
9. Yartseva S. Ponyatie yazykovoy interferentsii i ee tipov [The concept of language interference and its types] // Til va adabiyot ta'limi. – 2018. – No. 8. – P. 66.